

On the importance of multidisciplinary studies on insect vectors to better understand vector-borne plant diseases

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Insect vectors are key actors of the *Xylella fastidiosa* (Xf) pathosystem. Studies on their host plants, population dynamics and natural enemies as well as large-scale screening of populations for the presence of Xf are essential to understand and control the bacterium spread across agroecosystems. In this communication, we will summarize the studies conducted in Corsica since 2017 using field observations, molecular biology, statistical modeling and species distribution modelling. We will elaborate on results transferable to other European areas and, by contrast, on results indicating situations where a case-by-case management strategy appears more appropriate. We will report on the ecological factors driving the abundance of *Philaenus spumarius* (Ps), which is mostly associated with *Cistus monspeliensis* and shows preference for cool but relatively dry conditions. In Corsican agrosystems, Ps is not the only vector found on crop foliage and other insects could play a role for disease transmission. Managing *C. monspeliensis* in the vicinity of agricultural areas may nevertheless constitute a component of prophylaxis of Xf. We will also report on an egg parasitoid of Ps occurring throughout Europe that constitutes a potential control agent to be further evaluated. Finally, we will present the results of a massive screening of vectors conducted to assess the spatio-temporal prevalence of Xf. Results suggest that Xf introduction in Corsica largely predates its detection in 2015 and we hypothesize that ecological resilience of Corsican ecosystems could be possibly linked to plant diversity and lack of monoculture farming. Deciphering and managing the epidemiology of vector-borne plant diseases require multidisciplinary approaches and a thorough understanding of insect vector ecology in addition to the analysis of plant-pathogen interaction.